

Spectroscopic investigation of the reaction product of S_4N_3Cl with mercurous chloride

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The product of the reaction of S_4N_3Cl and $HgCl$ (non-aqueous media) is formulated as $(S_4N_3Cl.HgCl)_2$, a bidentated coordinated complex.

In continuation of our work on the reaction of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with copper and thorium¹, we report here the reaction of S_4N_3Cl with $HgCl$ in non-aqueous solvent leading to the formation of metal complex.

Results and Discussion

The grayish adduct obtained by the reaction of S_4N_3Cl and $HgCl$, is soluble in water. It decomposed above 300° to blackish solid. Elemental analyses reveal its formula $(S_4N_3Cl.HgCl)_2$.

The mass spectrum of the adduct shows signals, at m/z 107 (3 Cl), 167 (m-3) ($S_4N_3^+$), 426 ($S_4N_2Cl.HgCl$), 441 ($S_4N_3Cl.HgCl$), 512 ($S_4N_3Cl_3.HgCl$), 526 ($S_4N_4Cl_3.HgCl$), 542 ($S_4N_5Cl_3.HgCl$) and 661 [$(S_4N_3Cl)_3-S-N$], suggesting that S_4N_3Cl has coordinated with $HgCl$. The peaks at m/z 151, 391 and 735 are due to internal standard used. Other peaks in spectrum at m/z 217 (S_4N_3-S-N), 460 [$(S_4N_3Cl)-S_4N_4Cl_2$], 661 [$(S_4N_3Cl)_3-S-N$] and 751 [$(S_4N_3Cl)_3-(S-N)_3(M+2)$] are either the segment of S_4N_3Cl or its polymeric fragments formed during the exposure. The reactions of the formation of polymeric fragments may be explained as

for which the mass peak at m/z 441 (M-1) is observed. The complex on air-oxidation liberated metallic mercury,

This reaction is also confirmed by treating S_4N_3Cl with $HgCl_2$ as

The formation of $S_4N_3Cl_3$ has been inferred by the mass peak at m/z 512 for $S_4N_3Cl_3.HgCl$. The polymerization of $S_4N_3^+$ ions and S_4N_3Cl may be expressed as

IR spectral data of the adduct and the ligand are presented in Table 1. From these results, it is inferred that S_4N_3Cl has coordinated to $HgCl$ through its N coordinated S-N bands. In free S_4N_3Cl , the vibrations in the range 617.2–1107.1 cm^{-1} (S-N) shifted to higher frequencies explaining that S_4N_3Cl has bidentatedly coordinated to $HgCl$, forming its complex as shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. IR Spectral data of the complex

ν (cm^{-1})		% T	Assignment	Force const. $K \times 10^5$ dyne cm^2
Ligand	Complex			
455.2	464.8 (s)	84.190	N-S \rightarrow M	1.244
491.8	617.2 (s)	36.697	S-N-Free	2.193
617.2	694.2 (b)	69.470	S-N	2.775
1103.2	773.4 (s)	62.465	S-N \rightarrow M	3.443
140.2	1103.2 (b)	23.044	N-S-Cl	5.503
1739.7	1400.2 (s)	21.688	N-S-Cl	8.865
1967.3	2331.8 (b)	83.009	δ -S-N	31.299
2335.6	3031.9 (w)	36.972	δ -S-N	52.916
2366.5	3128.3 (b-d)	27.276	δ -S-N	56.334
2812.0	3759.0 (s)	61.385	δ -S-N	81.339

The electronic spectrum reveals two peaks at 204.4 and 279.2 nm; the former peak is due to charge transfer transition explaining the ionic form of $HgCl$ and S_4N_3Cl , while the latter assignment is due to $p\pi-p\pi$ transitions of S_4N_3Cl

Fig. 1. Structure of $[(S_4N_3Cl.HgCl)_2]_{2.03}$.

ring which coordinated to HgCl. This view is also supported by the values of frequency ratio ν_1/ν_2 less than one. The value of oscillator strength of the order of 10^{-5} expresses the presence of spin-allowed laporte forbidden transition inferring the spin-orbital coupling, that is formation of the $L \rightarrow M$ coordinated complex.

Experimental

S_4N_4 was prepared by reported method². S_4N_3Cl was prepared by the reaction of acetyl chloride with S_4N_4 as described³. The reaction of S_4N_3Cl with HgCl was carried out in DMF solution by refluxing for 24 h. The solid formed

was washed with DMF followed by ether and stored in vacuum. The molecular weight was determined by Rast's method using camphor as solvent. Mass spectrum was recorded on a Jeol S X 102 (FAB) spectrometer, IR spectrum on a Shimadzu 8201 P.C spectrophotometer and electronic spectrum on Hitachi 320, Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15U V/ VIS spectrophotometers.

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